

Narrating Belgian Business History

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Oral presentation

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Abstract

The BELHISFIRM project transforms over two centuries of Belgian corporate records into structured data, integrating them into the established SCOB firm-level research database. Published since 1873 in the Annexes of the Belgian Official Gazette (*Le Moniteur Belge*), these legal notices contain rich information on incorporations, capital structures, financial statements, securities holdings, mergers, and bankruptcies. Despite their historical value, their volume and heterogeneity have prevented systematic analysis. This project converts millions of archival fragments into a research infrastructure, linking them into coherent firm trajectories and networks spanning decades. We illustrate our approach through case studies, including Groupe Bruxelles Lambert (GBL). The presentation outlines our digital workflow: high-resolution scanning, automatic text recognition, named entity recognition, data reconciliation with existing datasets, and release as linked data on an interactive platform. The project demonstrates how large-scale archival digitization transforms complex corporate records into accessible narratives, enabling new forms of historical analysis and digital storytelling.

Methodology

The pipeline transforms historical corporate records into structured, machine-readable data through six stages:

1. **Digitization:** We compile a corpus of digital scans from the appendices of the Belgian State Gazette, provided by Erfgoedbibliotheek Antwerpen and digitized by a partner within the [BELHISFIRM](#) project.
2. **Automatic text recognition:** Company records in the appendices vary widely in length and feature irregular, often nested tabular layouts that complicate text segmentation and extraction. To ensure reliable output for downstream processing, we evaluated both traditional OCR engines and four recent vision–language models (VLMs), comparing their layout detection and text recognition accuracy to identify the most robust approach for this heterogeneous material.¹
3. **Layout classification:** This stage classifies and extracts structured layout components from digitized records, converting them into standardized representations.
4. **Named entity recognition:** Using FLAIR, extracted information is mapped onto core entity types (i.e. persons, companies) and normalized to ensure compatibility with the existing SCOB database.²
5. **Record linkage:** This stage performs entity disambiguation across records, reconstructing firm trajectories over time while handling name variants, spelling variation, and incomplete data. By establishing continuous identities, it enables the reconstruction of corporate histories and networks, transforming fragmented archival traces into coherent long-form narratives.
6. **Linked Data publication:** Processed data is structured according to the SCOB data model and represented in RDF using an adapted version of the [EURHISFIRM](#) data model to ensure semantic interoperability. The resulting linked data is published through a SAMPO-UI-based web platform supporting faceted search, browsing, and SPARQL querying for flexible exploration and visualization.³ These technical foundations allow users to engage with the data as dynamic, non-linear narratives that reveal corporate relationships and evolutions.

¹ Li, M., Lv, T., Chen, J., Cui, L., Lu, Y., Florencio, D., Zhang, C., Li, Z., & Wei, F. (2023). TrOCR: Transformer-Based Optical Character Recognition with Pre-trained Models. *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, 37(11), 13094-13102. <https://doi.org/10.1609/aaai.v37i11.26538>
Wei, H., Sun, Y., & Li, Y. (2025). Deepseek-ocr: Contexts optical compression. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.18234*.

Semnani, S., Zhang, H., He, X., Tekgürler, M., & Lam, M. (2025, November). CHURRO: Making History Readable with an Open-Weight Large Vision-Language Model for High-Accuracy, Low-Cost Historical Text Recognition. In *Proceedings of the 2025 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing* (pp. 34765-34812).

Yang, A., Li, A., Yang, B., Zhang, B., Hui, B., Zheng, B., ... & Qiu, Z. (2025). Qwen3 technical report. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.09388*.

² Akbik, A., Bergmann, T., Blythe, D., Rasul, K., Schweter, S., & Vollgraf, R. (2019, June). FLAIR: An easy-to-use framework for state-of-the-art NLP. In *Proceedings of the 2019 conference of the North American chapter of the association for computational linguistics (demonstrations)* (pp. 54-59).

³ Ikkala, Esko, Eero Hyvönen, Heikki Rantala, and Mikko Koho. "Sampo-UI: A full stack JavaScript framework for developing semantic portal user interfaces." *Semantic Web* 13, no. 1 (2021): 69-84.

Results

ATR evaluation has been completed and reveals substantive differences between traditional ATR systems and recent vision-language models.⁴ VLMs demonstrate superior performance on complex layouts and degraded documents but introduce a qualitatively different error profile than conventional OCR.⁵ These errors prove difficult to detect automatically as they require domain knowledge to identify. Given the scale of the corpus (millions of pages), we are also exploring partial semi-automation through AI-based systems to monitor selected data-quality metrics.⁶

For digitized appendices currently available, company records undergo automatic text recognition followed by layout segmentation (corporate headings, tables, etc.). Named entity recognition then extracts entities relevant to the SCOB data model. These entities are disambiguated at the record level, across years, and ultimately across the entire corpus. Following record linkage, the resulting data is ingested into the SCOB database and mapped to an RDF structure for the linked-data public platform.

The SAMPO-UI web platform enables users to query RDF-encoded company records through multiple complementary views (firm view and securities view), each supporting filtering based on various variables (see Figure 1). These tools allow users to trace firms across successive notices, reconstruct board compositions and ownership networks, and export structured datasets for further analysis. This functionality supports the reconstruction of long-term corporate trajectories, revealing how firms evolve, intersect, and shape socio-economic dynamics over time. All datasets are made openly available where possible, with GDPR-sensitive information appropriately restricted.

⁴ Vercruyse, B. and Vincent Ducatteeuw, Easy as 1-2-3? Vision-Language Models for Historical Text Recognition in *Journal of Digital History*, accepted.

⁵ see also: Levchenko, Maria. "Evaluating LLMs for Historical Document OCR: A Methodological Framework for Digital Humanities." arXiv preprint arXiv:2510.06743 (2025).

⁶ <https://github.com/GhentCDH/BelHisFirm-BelHisHAAI>

Results: 52 corporations

Active filters: Country France (x) Name(s) banque (x) REMOVE ALL

Narrow down by:

Name(s)

Legal form

Date of Founding

Date of Dissolution

Street Address

City

Search...

- Paris [39]
- Onbekend [8]
- Paris IXe [4]
- Parijs [2]
- Constantinopel [1]
- Lyon [1]
- Nancy [1]
- onbekend [1]
- Paris (IX) [1]
- Roubaix [1]

Country

Search...

- Belgique [448]
- Onbekend [361]
- France [52]
- Frankrijk [7]
- Rusland [5]
- Nederland [4]
- Oostenrijk-Hongarije [4]
- België [3]
- Bulgarije [3]
- Egypte [3]

id	Name(s)	Legal form	address(es)	Date of Founding
	Banque de l'Union Franco-Belge	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Rue du Quatre Septembre 12 Paris France	1872-04-21 00:00:00
	Banque de Paris et des Pays-Bas	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Paris France ...	1872-01-27 00:00:00
	Société Française de Banque	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Paris France ...	-
	Banque Impériale Ottomane	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Constantinopel Ottomaanse Rijk ...	-
	Banque Nationale d'Algé	-	Paris France ...	1881-05-12 00:00:00
	Société Française de Banques et de Dépôts	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	boulevard Hausmann 29 (RF 1933 II 1370) Paris IXe France ...	1898-03-05 00:00:00
	Banque de Bordeaux	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Bordeaux France ...	1899-09-21 00:00:00
	Banque de Java (Javaasche Bank) (S.A. obéfi)	-	Blanc-Misseron-Crespin (Nord) France	1909-08-02 00:00:00
	Banque Nationale de Saint-Domingue	-	Paris France	1889-10-08 00:00:00
	Banque spéciale des Valeurs Industrielles	-	• Paris France • 132, rue Réaumur Paris France	1897-12-27 00:00:00
	Banque Parisienne	-	Paris France ...	1874-04-07 00:00:00
	Banque hypothécaire franco-argentine	-	Paris France ...	-
	Société Nouvelle de la Banque de l'Ouest	-	Paris France ...	-
	Banque Foncière de Paris	Société anonyme (Naamloze vennootschap)	Paris France ...	1852-07-29 00:00:00
	Banque Commerciale et Industrielle	-	Onbekend France ...	1880-07-01 00:00:00
	Banque de l'Union Parisienne	-	Onbekend Onbekend ...	1904-01-16 00:00:00
	Banque Nationale pour le Commerce et l'Industrie	-	boulevard des Italiens 16 (RF 1938 I 1205) Paris (IX) France ...	-
	Banque de Consignations	-	rue Saint-Lazare 54 Paris France	1880-08-28 00:00:00
	Banque des Fonds publics et des Valeurs Industrielles	-	place de la Bourse 1 et 3 Paris France	1877-02-19 00:00:00
	Crédit Colonial (S.A.)	-	Onbekend France ...	1860-10-12 00:00:00
	Banque Suisse et Française	-	Paris France ...	1894-06-08 00:00:00
	Banque Transatlantique (à Paris)	-	Paris France ...	1881-08-25 00:00:00
	Caisse Commerciale de Saint-Quentin (anciennement Caisse Léoyer)	-	Saint-Quentin France	1841-02-17 00:00:00
	Adrien Bénard et Stanismond Jastrzewski (Banque)	-	Paris France ...	-
	Banque de France	-	Paris France ...	-
	Banque française pour le Commerce et l'Industrie	-	Paris France ...	1901-07-26 00:00:00
	Banque Internationale de Paris	-	Paris France ...	1894-06-08 00:00:00
	Banque Oustic et Cie - Paris	-	Paris France ...	-
	Banque de l'Indochine (S.A. française)	-	Paris France ...	-
	Banque régionale du Nord	-	Roubaix France ...	-
	Banque Internationale de Commerce (à Paris)	-	Onbekend France ...	-
	Banque Pétrard, Mabilly et Cie	-	RF 1933 III 699 Onbekend France	-
	Banque Adam	-	Onbekend France ...	-

Figure 1. Faceted search interface on the SAMPO-based web platform (work in progress), filtering companies containing "banque" and operating in France.

Contribution

This project makes three scholarly contributions. First, it introduces BELHISFIRM, an end-to-end infrastructure for transforming archival company records into accessible research data through data processing and public dissemination. Second, it provides systematic evidence on vision-language model performance for automatic text recognition of semi-structured historical documents, offering practical guidance for large-scale digitization initiatives. Third, it enhances methodological transparency by documenting the pipeline's rationale, highlighting existing but modified tools (e.g. VLMs, refined record linkage method) and newly developed AI-based automation for detecting and diagnosing data issues. This documentation allows others to assess and adapt BELHISFIRM to different archival contexts.